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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**A Case Report****A RARE CASE REPORT ON MAGNESIUM SULPHATE
OINTMENT INDUCED SKIN RASHES****Jeethu K Shaji^{1*}, Shalin Elsy Varghese¹, Elza Mathew¹, Apollo James², S. Haja Sherief³
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Abstract:

Skin reactions are often seen as a common adverse drug reaction in hospitalized patients with an incidence of 2-3% [1]. Magnesium Sulfate is usually applied as a “drawing ointment” for boils, carbuncles and other skin infections [2]. Magnesium sulfate ointment contains dried MgSO₄ 64%, phenol 0.5%, glycerin q.s. Phenol has side effects of skin rashes. Here we have reported a case of skin rashes which was worsened due to MgSO₄ ointment application.

Keywords: MgSO₄, Lipid Profile Tests, COPD, Rashes***Corresponding Author:****Jeethu K Shaji,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Magnesium sulphate is also commonly referred to as Epsom salt. This name was derived from the town of Epsom, which is where the salt was originally distilled. Magnesium sulphate is used to help reduce the appearance of skin pruritus, soothing the pain of sore throat and as a method of reducing inflammation often as a method of reducing inflammation often through soaking the compound in through the skin. MgSO₄ ointment which was applied as anti-inflammatory on the red rashes had 0.5% phenol in it. Phenol can come in contact with the skin and it can penetrate through it and causes irritations. Here, we report a case of magnesium sulphate ointment induced skin rashes.

CASE REPORT:

A 68 year old female patient was admitted to the hospital with complaints of sudden onset of weakness in left side of the body, slurring of

speech and deviation of mouth. Patient was not able to stand of her own. She had a history of on and off fever and respiratory problem. She was also a chronic smoker. Patient had comorbidities of hypertension and COPD and is under tablet Amlolol AT not regularly and Neb Asthalin. The patient was started with IV medication like Augmentin, Enoxaparin and so on. On the third day, after removing the cannula, red rashes appeared on the inserted area. Then immediately MgSO₄ ointment was applied over the area. The skin rashes got worsened. On the fourth day, the rashes turned out to be black in color [3,5]. Mupirocin ointment was applied over the area as the treatment medication. On observing the laboratory parameters, lipid profile tests were elevated as the patient was obese. Her complete blood count was also seen elevated. [8,9]

DISCUSSION:

Topical medications can worsen the skin reaction. Here the MgSO₄ ointment which was applied as anti-inflammatory on the red rashes had 0.5% phenol in it. Phenol can come in contact with the skin and it can penetrate through it and causes irritations. So the blackening of the rashes were diagnosed to be the complication of the topical ointment [7].

CONCLUSION:

Topical ointments might have complications or side effects of skin reactions [4,6]. So before application, the drug should be properly monitored and only then it should be applied.

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